

ADHESION OF DISSIMILAR POLYMER-METAL COMPOSITE MATERIAL BY MECHANICAL INTERLOCKING

Harrison Lin¹, Adam Pearson¹, Yasamin Kazemi¹, Marcus Heydrich², Ahmed Hammami², Adel Kakroodi², Hani E. Naguib¹
 1 Department of Mechanical & Industrial Engineering, University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada,
 2 Shawcor Ltd., Toronto, Canada

Introduction

This study is focused on developing a new class of polymer-metal composites (PMC) with strong interfacial adhesion by mechanism of mechanical interlocking. Engineering thermoplastic polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) and 1100 grade aluminum alloy were used for the fabrication of the PMCs. Adhesion mechanism of mechanical interlocking was used to adhere polymer to etched microstructure surface of the aluminum, without the use of an adhesive agent. The mechanism of mechanical interlocking results in the penetration of polymer into the micro-pores of the aluminum substrate contributing to improved bond strength.

Objective

- Enhance adhesion between dissimilar organic and inorganic materials without the use of adhesives
- Optimization of fabrication processing conditions (temperature, pressure and time) for improved adhesion, evaluated by T-peel testing of the interfacial adhesion strength

PMC Fabrication

Lay-up of PMC samples for T-peel evaluation

Vacuum bagging compression molding

- Vacuum bagging mitigates presence of air entrapment at the bonded interface between PPS and aluminum during compression molding
- Prior to fabricating the PMC specimens, the etched aluminum sheets were cleaned for 10 minutes by ultrasonication in deionized water to remove any remaining contaminants on the surface, inhibit bonding of the polymer to the microstructured substrate
- Optimization conditions evaluated: Temperature (290°C, 300°C, 320°C), pressure (1, 2, 5 tons), time (1, 5 min)

Adhesion Testing by T-peel and SEM Analysis

1. Temperature optimization

2. Pressure optimization

3. Time optimization

4. Compression/vacuum opt.

A. Smooth Aluminum

B. Etched Aluminum

C. PPS-Aluminum

- Etched microstructures have a higher roughness value and a lower contact angle
- Post T-peel test samples show adhesive/cohesive failure at the aluminum interface owing to interlocking of PPS to the etched micro-pores
- Temperature above 300°C produces excess entrapped air causing ununiform bonding during processing
- Longer processing time enables more resin to penetrate and flow into the etched micro-pores, allowing more resin to establish contact and improve bonding at the interface
- Vacuum bagging compression molding process improves the bond strength significantly by mitigating the presence of entrapped air formation during processing, ensuring maximum surface adhesion interaction at the PPS-aluminum interface